

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Chemical composition and digestibility of urea-treated rice straw

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The straw of seven rice cultivars, grown during 1993 under uniform agronomic conditions, were treated with 3%, 4%, or no urea. Their chemical composition (Table 1), nylon bag organic matter digestibility (NBOMD), and nylon bag neutral detergent fiber digestibility (NBNDFD) were determined (Table 2).

The crude protein (CP) content in untreated Basmati 370, Sita, Cauvery, Pant Dhan 6, and Saket 4 was higher than that in Pusa Basmati and Kasturi (Table 1). The ash content in untreated cultivars

Saket 4, Kasturi, and Pant Dhan 6 was more than the mean value of 151 g/kg dry matter (DM). The neutral detergent fiber (NDF) content in the untreated straw varied from 728 to 778 g/kg DM.

Treating straw with urea increased ash content and decreased organic matter (OM) content of straw. Straw with a higher ash content has a lower energy value. The NDF content increased in cultivars Kasturi and Pusa Basmati. whereas in the others it declined when treated with 3% urea and even more with 4% urea. Treating with 3% urea increased the CP content to 119 g/kg DM and with 4% to 136 g/kg DM.

The NBOMD and NBNDFD of straw from the cultivars differed significantly (Table 2). There was no significant difference between 3 and 4% urea treatments. The improvement in digestibility was greater in straw that had lower digestibility prior to urea treatment.

The relationship between NBNDFD of treated straw (Y) and NBNDFD of untreated straw (x) was $Y = 788 - 1.35x$ ($r^2 = 0.76$, $n = 7$) for 3% urea-treated straw and $Y = 681 - 1.15x$ ($r^2 = 0.75$, $n = 7$) for 4% urea-treated straw. This emphasized that for increased profitability, rice straw with higher digestibility may be fed to animals without urea treatment. ■

Effect of root pruning during ripening on grain filling in rice

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The positive contribution of roots during the ripening phase to grain filling has been suggested in many reports. However, the discussion seems to have been speculative, with higher yield sometimes being observed where most of the roots are black and necrotic at ripening.

We evaluated how roots contribute to grain filling when pruned at different times around heading. High-yielding semidwarf cultivar IR58 was transplanted at the beginning of Jul and Aug 1989 (wet season) at IRRI at a density of 50 hills/m². We applied a total of 150 kg N/ha during the entire growing season. A sickle was used to prune, at night, all of the roots (at the base of the hill) for 20 plants in the middle of a 30-m² plot. Each pruned hill was lifted once into the air to ensure the plant was completely separated from the ground and then returned to the same place.

Each treated plant was tied to a stick inserted into the soil beside the hill. This kept the plants erect and avoided disturbances in the canopy structure from affecting grain filling. Roots were pruned at different times before and after heading with three replications. Grain yield and yield components were determined using conventional methods.

The sudden decrease of surface area for water absorption after pruning caused

Table 1. Differences in chemical composition of straw of cultivars untreated and treated with urea (g/kg DM). Uttar Pradesh, India. 1993.

Variety	Untreated			3% urea-treated			4% urea-treated		
	Ash	NDF	CP	Ash	NDF	CP	Ash	NDF	CP
Basmati 370	129	763	54	142	755	113	136	768	140
Pusa Basmati	148	778	46	154	810	106	157	768	125
Sita	142	728	65	159	768	130	157	748	145
Kasturi	161	768	49	165	810	121	164	753	137
Cauvery	158	763	37	162	731	133	151	751	141
Pant Dhan 6	158	752	68	170	747	109	158	727	130
Saket 4	170	737	70	181	738	121	170	723	136
Mean	151	755	61	162	765	119	156	748	136

Table 2. Nylon bag organic matter digestibility (NBOMD) and nylon bag neutral detergent fiber digestibility (NBNDFD) (72h) of rice straw of different cultivars. Uttar Pradesh, India. 1993.

Variety	NBOMD (g/kg)			NBNDFD (g/kg)		
	Unit	3% urea-treated	4% urea-treated	Unit	3% urea-treated	4% urea-treated
Sita	547	653	680	439	634	615
Pusa Basmati	573	669	698	496	627	652
Kasturi	570	676	669	519	640	606
Pant Dhan 6	596	684	665	507	620	584
Saket 4	584	658	667	493	576	590
Basmati 370	597	645	651	523	579	605
Cauvery	615	663	670	540	588	604
Mean ± SEM	582 ± 8.9	664	672	50.3 ± 34.0	605	608
CD (P = .01)	36.2			34.0		
CD (P = .05)	26.4			24.8		

Effect of root pruning at various times during ripening on IR58 grain yield and its components. IRRI, 1989.

Treatment	Time of treatment (DAH) ^a	Grain yield			Filled grains (%)	Grain weight (mg)
		Actual (g/m ²)	sd ^b	Corrected ^c (g/m ²)		
Control (Jul planting)		337	29	337	64	18.7
Roots pruned	-5	190	21	217	47	16.6
	0	290	15	273	56	17.3
	5	350	40	306	62	17.5
	10	320	22	324	64	18.0
Control (Aug planting)		426	31	426	71	21.3
Roots pruned	-5	355	25	334	62	19.1
	0	350	31	389	66	20.9
	5	380	19	408	71	20.4
	10	406	48	364	67	19.3
	15	385	35	398	71	19.9

^a Days after heading. ^b Standard deviation. ^c Corrected yield assuming spikelet number is the same as in the control plot.

leaves to curl slightly the next day. Little wilting, however, was observed on the second day after pruning and none after that.

Both grain weight and ripening percentage decreased in all the treated plots (see table). The reduction in ripening percentage was higher when roots were pruned earlier, the time during which fertilization and initial grain growth occur—and when plants are most sensitive to water imbalance.

Grain yield was reduced markedly when treated before heading and by about 10% when plants were treated at 5 d after heading and later, despite the complete removal of roots (see figure). Active nutrient uptake and the supply of cytokinins from the roots might have been reduced completely because the roots and root zone were removed. Few new roots formed in the pruned plants.

Neither the nutrient uptake nor the supply of plant hormones from the roots

Effect of root pruning on grain yield of IR58. IRRI, 1989.

at this growth stage seem to be the major factor for grain filling. The principal contribution of roots to ripening is to supply sufficient water and to support the top of the plant. Grain yield was not so high in the wet weason, so the required nutrients after heading may have been smaller. Similar experiments during the dry season, when yields are higher, would help further elucidate the contribution of roots to grain filling in rice. ■

Mineral elements in Australian brown rice

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Ninety samples of brown rice from popular cultivar Amaroo were collected from commercial crops in the irrigated rice-growing regions of southern Australia at the end of the 1991-92 season. The samples were analyzed for total N using the Kjeldahl technique and for P, K, Mg, S, Ca, Mn, Na, Al, Zn, Fe, Cu, and Mo using inductively coupled plasma emission spectroscopy.

The range and mean concentrations of each element were summarized from this study and ranges reported in 22 previous studies from Southeast Asia and the USA (Table 1). Many samples in earlier studies were from crops grown under experimental conditions with various nutrient inputs. Mean concentrations of

Table 1. Comparison of elemental composition of brown rice from Australia and that reported in previous studies (all values on oven-dry weight basis).

Element	Australian crops (mean)	Range	
		This study	Previous studies ^a
		(g/kg)	
Nitrogen	13.7	11.0 - 17.0	na
Phosphorus	3.4	2.8 - 3.6	2.0 - 5.0
Potassium	2.8	2.4 - 3.5	0.7 - 3.3
Magnesium	1.3	1.2 - 1.5	0.2 - 1.7
Sulfur	1.1	0.9 - 1.3	0.3 - 2.2
Calcium	0.1	0.03 - 0.13	0.1 - 0.6
		(mg/kg)	
Manganese	48	29 - 70	2.3 - 42
Sodium	23	0 - 221	20 - 395
Zinc	19	15 - 24	7 - 33
Iron	15	6 - 78	2.3 - 60
Aluminum	15	0.6 - 42	0.3 - 30
Copper	5	1.6 - 15	1.2 - 7
Molybdenum	0.8	0 - 2	0.3 - 1.2

^a Based on data from 22 independent studies in Southeast Asia and the USA.

all mineral nutrients in Australian grain fell into the ranges found in earlier studies, except for Mn, which was generally at higher concentrations, and Ca, which was at lower concentrations. Some samples had higher Fe, Al, and Cu

concentrations than reported for samples from Southeast Asia and the USA, but some of these may have been contaminated by these elements during grinding. Grain in the previous studies also had a greater range of P and Na concentrations.